

NOTES

Zeolite Supported Interaction of Copper(II) and Fast Sulphon Black F: A Thermogravimetric, IR Spectroscopic and X-ray Diffraction Study

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THE organic dye, Fast Sulphon Black F (colour index 306) is the sodium salt of 1-hydroxy-8-(2-hydroxynaphthyl azo)-2-(sulphonaphthyl azo)-3,6-disulphonic acid. It forms a red complex with copper(II) ion in ammoniacal medium. The present work is devoted to the study of the interaction of the dye and copper(II) in presence of ammonia using synthetic zeolite 3A as the supporting medium. A blue adsorbed derivative, instead of the expected red complex, is formed. The solid zeolite support, therefore, brings about a new type of interaction. The thermochemical changes of the adsorbed derivative and its structure have been investigated by thermogravimetric, ir spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction methods. The X-ray data of the blue adsorbed derivative and its preheated brown residue have been compared with the X-ray data of both 3A zeolite and its copper(II) exchanged form¹. Activation energy of the thermochemical processes have been evaluated from the TG data².

Experimental

The details of the procedure used for sample preparation have been mentioned in the previous communication³. The synthetic zeolite 3A ($K_{12}Al_{12}Si_{12}O_{48} \cdot 21H_2O$, Union Carbide Corp., USA) was used to adsorb the dye in an aqueous medium. The dye adsorbed sample was then treated with aqueous copper(II) sulphate-pentahydrate and ammonia and a blue adsorbed derivative resulted. The air-dried (~ 373 K) blue derivative was used for recording the TG data in air on a FCIL (Sindri) thermobalance upto 1273 K at a heating rate of $10^\circ \text{ min}^{-1}$. The resultant brown residue left in the TG balance was used to further record its TG behaviour and the two plots shown in Fig. 1. The ir spectra of the original blue adsorbed derivative of 3A and its two preheated residues obtained after TG analysis were recorded between 5000 and 650 cm^{-1} in KBr pellets on a Spektromom 2000 spectrophotometer. The X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 2) of the zeolite samples were obtained using a Philips PW 1140 X-ray unit. The thermal data have been reproduced in Table 1.

Fig. 1. TG plots between 293 and 1253 K: I original blue 3A zeolite (wt. 188.5 mg); II preheated brown residue (wt. 117.0 mg).

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffractograms of I and II after TG analysis upto 1273 K.

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF THERMAL DATA

Zeolite	Wt. loss %	Temp K	Activation energy kJ mol^{-1}		
			From $\ln g(\infty)/T^2$ vs $10^3/T$ plots		
			n=1	n=2	n=3
Blue adsorbed derivative of 3A	24.7	293-693	43.8	30.6	26.0
	2.1	713-833	53.5	41.6	38.1
	2.9	873-1013	88.8	62.3	57.1
	6.1	1013-1253	287.5	166.6	120.9
Preheated (1273 K) brown residue	2.1	653-713	420.9	236.9	165.0

Results and Discussion

TG plot of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A zeolite can be resolved easily into four parts indicating various thermochemical changes. These changes occur over distinguishable temperature limits. Kinetics of these thermal events can be evaluated from the rate of change in weight with time and computation of activation energies indicates the nature of the thermochemical processes. While non-linear plots were obtained for $g(\alpha)$ vs time for $n=1, 2$ and 3 , linear plots were obtained for $\ln[g(\alpha)/T^n]$ vs $1000/T$. The first major step of weight loss occurs between 293 and 693 K, attributed to dehydration, loss of ammonia and the desorption of the organic dye. Further dehydration occurs between 713 and 833 K followed by deammoniation, dehydroxylation and formation of oxide residue from 873 K. However, the zeolite remains stable. Collapse of the alumino-silicate structure occurs only after the residue after initial TG analysis upto 1273 K is further heated to eliminate residual water molecules. The brownish residue shows loss of weight of only 2.1% between 633 and 713. The presence of an oxide residue was found⁴ at 603 K in the investigation of the thermal behaviour of Cu(II)-Y zeolite. Similarly deammoniation of ammonium X zeolite showed loss of physical water at 373 K and ammonia dissociation from small pores at 448 K and from large pores between 453 and 623 K. For $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Y zeolite deammoniation took place at 70° higher than the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -X zeolite⁵. Dehydroxylation occurred for $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Y around 923 K. The thermal behaviour of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A zeolite can thus be compared with the known behaviours of other zeolite samples.

The ir spectra of the new blue derivative exhibit prominent absorption bands at 3300, 1640 and 1000 cm^{-1} . A shoulder at 1440 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 1400 cm^{-1} indicate interaction of ammonia with Cu(II) cation. The ir spectra of the residue after heating to 1273 K exhibit only a weak peak at 3200 cm^{-1} and a broad and shallow peak between 1300 and 960 cm^{-1} . Heating eliminates both the physically adsorbed water and the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ cation as indicated by the disappearance of bands at 1640 and 1400 cm^{-1} . X-ray diffraction studies of hydrated $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ -Mordenite⁶ revealed that deposition of amorphous alumina occurred in the pores as a result of heating. This was also indicated by shifts in the ir spectra in the framework region which showed that the crystal became more siliceous on heating. The present studies of thermal behaviour of the blue adsorbed derivative of 3A-zeolite indicate similar structural changes. Moreover, the prior adsorption of Fast Sulphon Black F dye on the zeolite prevents the expected complex formation reaction with the copper(II) cation in presence of ammonia. Interaction with ammonia leads to the formation of copper(II) amine complex as well as the $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ cation. Earlier work on ammonia adsorption on A-zeolites showed formation of two species, ammonia molecules hydrogen bonded to the

lattice oxygen or coordinated to the metal ion and $\text{NH}_4(\text{I})$ ions located on Bronsted sites⁷.

The d spacings and the intensities were obtained from the X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 2) with respect to CuK_α radiation of wavelength 1.5418 Å. These data indicate much variations. These differences in d spacings for Cu(II)-3A zeolite and the new blue derivative and its preheated form can be attributed to the presence of the interacted species in the blue derivative and the structural changes brought about by thermal events.

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Stability Constants of Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Hexachlorophene

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HEXACHLOROPHENE, 2,2-methylene bis(3,4,6-trichlorophenol), has got much utility due to its antibacterial activity. Its solid chelates have been reported in literature^{1,2}. In continuation of our previous work³ on the stability of its complexes of metal ions, the proton ligand stability constants of hexachlorophene and stabilities of its complexes with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are reported at 25 and 45° with ionic strength 0.1 M and at 35° with ionic strengths 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M in alcohol-water system (1 : 1, v/v).

Experimental

The reagents were AnalaR. Deionised water was used for making all the solutions. Carbon dioxide free KOH (0.1 M) solution was used for potentiometric titrations. The solutions of metal ions were standardized to 0.01 M . Hexachlorophene was dissolved in absolute alcohol to prepare 0.05 M solution. 0.05 M HClO_4 was used. The ionic strength was maintained with 1.0 M NaClO_4 .

Systronics 322-1 pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly was used and standardised with